

BC-SIM-TR-038

SIMBIO-SYS ICO#04b

Interchannel Test Report

Michele Zusi¹, Emanuele Simioni², Vincenzo Della Corte¹, Andrea Cichetti¹,
Romolo Politi¹,
Gabriele Cremonese², Fabrizio Capaccioni¹, Alain Doressundiram³,
Pasquale Palumbo¹, Cristina Re², Mathieu Vincendon⁴

¹INAF-IAPS, Via Fosso del Cavaliere 100, 00133, Rome, Italy

²INAF-OAPd, Vicolo Osservatorio 5, 35122, Padua, Italy

³LESIA (Observatoire de Paris - PSL, Laboratoire d'Études Spatiales et d'Instrumentation en Astrophysique), 92195 Meudon Cedex, France

⁴CNRS (Institut d'Astrophysique Spatiale), Université Paris Sud, 91405, Orsay, France

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Approvation

Edited by:	Michele Zusi
	Emanuele Simioni
	Vincenzo Della Corte
	Andrea Cicchetti
Approved by:	Fabrizio Capaccioni
	Cristina Re
	Pasquale Palumbo
	Gabriele Cremonese

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1.Introduction

1.1. Scope

This document contains the results and the discussion on the interchannel tests performed during the Instrument check Out 04bis (ICO#04b) for the Spectrometers and Imagers for MPO BepiColombo Integrated Observatory SYStem (SIMBIO-SYS) described in [RD.1].

The ICO#04b was requested by the SIMBIO-SYS team to repeat the instruments not completely executed during ICO#04 tests [RD.2]. In particular, SIMBIO-SYS repeated the Interchannel test performed during previous ICO04 [RD.3] but limited to HRIC and STC Channels.

1.2. Reference documents

- [RD.1] BC-SIM-PL-007_-_SIMBIO-SYS_Checkout_04b_Test_Summary_Issue1_Revision0, [10.5281/zenodo.10035541](https://zenodo.org/record/10035541)
- [RD.2] BC-SIM-PL-006_-_SIMBIO-SYS_Checkout_04_Test_Summary_Issue1_Revision0, [10.20371/INAF/TechRep/204](https://www.inaf.it/INAF/TechRep/204)
- [RD.3] BC-SIM-TR-034_-_SIMBIO-SYS_ICO#04_Interchannel_Test_Report_Issue1_Revision0, [10.5281/zenodo.8366159](https://zenodo.org/record/8366159)
- [RD.4] BC-SIM-TN-003_-_Reports_and_Note_Layout_and_Flow, [10.20371/INAF/TechRep/36](https://www.inaf.it/INAF/TechRep/36)
- [RD.5] BC-ALS-TN-00099 MPO PFM Monitoring Thermistors Location
- [RD.6] BC-SIM-GAF-MA-002 rev.8_SIMBIO-SYS FM User Manual, 2017
- [RD.7] BC-SIM-TR-036_-_EGSE_ICO4B_Report, [10.5281/zenodo.10068973](https://zenodo.org/record/10068973)
- [RD.8] BC-SIM-TR-037_-_VIHI_ICO#04b_report
- [RD.9] BC-SIM-TN-004_-_SIMBIO-SYS_FOP_update_after_NECF, [10.20371/INAF/TechRep/58](https://www.inaf.it/INAF/TechRep/58)

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[RD.10]BC-SIM-TR-035_-_SIMBIO-SYS_ICO#04_Test_Report_Issue1_Revision0,
[10.5281/zenodo.10014954](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10014954)

[RD.11]BC-SIM-TR-021_-_SIMBIO-SYS_ICO#02_Test_Report_Issue1_Revision0,
[10.20371/INAF/TechRep/146](https://doi.org/10.20371/INAF/TechRep/146)

1.3. Acronyms

ASW	Application SoftWare
ACK	Acknowledgement
CF	Cold Finger
dNECP	delta Near Earth Commissioning Phase
FPA	Focal Plane Assembly
FOP	Flight Operation Procedure
HK	Housekeeping
HRIC	High spatial Resolution Imaging Channel
ME	Main Electronics
NECP	Near Earth Commissioning Phase
OBCP	On-Board Control Procedure
PDOR	Payload Direct Operation Request
PE	Proximity Electronics
SIMBIO-SYS	Spectrometers and Imagers for MPO BepiColombo Integrated Observatory SYSTEM
SSMM	Solid State Mass Memory
STC	STereo imaging Channel
S/C	Space-Craft
TC	TeleCommand
TEC	Thermo-Electric Cooler
VIHI	VIsible and Hyper-spectral Imaging channel

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1.4. Document format and repository

This document is compliant with the SIMBIO-SYS Report and Note Layout and Flow [RD.4] and will be archived on the SIMBIO-SYS ZENODO community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/?p=SIMBIO-SYS>), on the INAF Open Access repository and the SIMBIO-SYS team Archive.

1.5. Document organization

This document is organized in sections whose topics are listed as follows:

- Section 2 – SIMBIO-SYS thermal environment description, with a brief description of the aboard units and sensors used to control the operative temperature of the instrument during the test
- Section 3 – Interchannel test results and discussion
- Section 4 – Some conclusions on the ICO04b activities are reported

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2.SIMBIO-SYS thermal environment description

The SIMBIO-SYS thermal environment is controlled by means of the Space-Craft (S/C) dedicated Cold Fingers (CFs) and several thermal sensors which are described in the following subsections.

2.1. SIMBIO-SYS CF sensors

In the following table the list of CF temperature sensors for the three channels is reported. To note that all sensors are fixed on the S/C CF.

Channel	Sensor name	ESA ID	THALES ID
HRIC	MPO-TEMP-SIMBIO-HRIC-CF	NRUD2079	THT-B6T133
STC	MPO-TEMP-SIMBIO-STC-CF	NRUD2087	THT-B6T136
VIHI	MPO-TEMP-SIMBIO-VIHI-CF	NRUD2091	THT-B6T137

Table 1: CF sensors of the SIMBIO-SYS channels together with their reference to ESA and Theles Alenia nomenclature (see [RD.5] for details)

For more details on their positions see [RD.5].

During the execution of the ICO#04b tests its value was monitored with a 5-minute frequency; the obtained trend is reported in Figure 1.

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Figure 1: SIMBIO-SYS Cold Finger temperature during the ICO#04b tests. Temperature is reported in °C.

Figure 1 shows that all **SIMBIO-SYS CFs** reached the **temperature thresholds** after 2 h of heating and **maintained the instrument at the expected temperature for all the duration of the test.**

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2.2. SIMBIO-SYS thermal sensors

For the monitoring of its thermal behaviour, the SIMBIO-SYS instrument is equipped by the following sensors:

- **HRIC**

Table 2 reports the main HRIC sensors covering the temperature measurement of the Focal Plane Assembly (FPA), the Proximity Electronics (PE), the backside of the detector and the HRIC Optical Bench (OB), the Current and the Voltage measurement of the Thermo-Electric Cooler (TEC) and the PE.

Param Id	Param Name	Unit	Calibration
NSS11040	HRIC Temperature FPA1	K	CSSP0010TM
NSS11041	HRIC Temperature FPA2	K	CSSP0011TM
NSS11042	HRIC Temperature PE	K	CSSP0012TM
NSS11043	HRIC Temp Tele1	K	CSSP0013TM
NSS11044	HRIC Temp Tele2	K	CSSP0014TM
NSS11050	HRIC PE 3.3V Measured	V	CSSP0015TM
NSS11051	HRIC TEC Current	A	CSSP0016TM

Table 2: Main HRIC temperature sensors of the FPA, PE, the backside of the detector and the HRIC OB as reported in [RD.5]. All HKs are part of the Packet YSS40001.

Table 3 and Figure 2 report the position of the above listed sensors.

Unit	Instrument Controlled Thermistors	Temp.	Location	Parameter
HRIC Optics 1	PT1000	-40/65	TIRD filter	HRIC_Temp_Tele_1
HRIC Optics 2	PT1000	-40/65	FPA package	HRIC_Temp_Tele_2
HRIC SCA 1	DT470	-40/65	FPA SCA	HRIC_Temp_FPA_1
HRIC SCA 2	DT470	-40/65	FPA SCA	HRIC_Temp_FPA_2
HRIC PE	PT1000	-40/65	PE hot spot	HRIC_Temp_PE

Table 3: HRIC temperature sensor position.

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Figure 2: HRIC-FPA temperature sensors [RD.6] next to the FPA, called SCA1 (on the left) and SCA2 (on the right) and associated respectively to the NSS11040 and NSS11041.

- **STC**

PACKET ID: YSS40002		
Param ID	Param Name	Unit
NSS21040	Temperature FPA1	K
NSS21041	Temperature FPA2	K
NSS21042	Temperature PE	K
NSS21043	Temp FPA_Package	K
NSS21044	Temp OpticalBench	K

Table 4: Main SIMB STC Housekeeping (Packed ID YSS40002) including temperature sensors of STC on the FPA, PE, the backside of the detector and the STC OB as Reported in [RD.6].

The position of the temperature sensors are shown in Figure 3 extracted from [RD.6].

The STC Temperature FPA1 and FPA2 sensors, hereafter abbreviated with TFPA1 and TFPA2 respectively, are located close to the detector surface (see Figure 3). Their measures indicate an increase in the temperature when the detector is switched on and then a lowering after the TEC switching on; their temperature values are also used as feedback for interpreting the TEC behavior.

The Temp Channel-fw sensor, defined as the Focal Plane Assembly (FPA) Package in EGSE [RD.7] is located on the hot side of the FPA package, thus

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it is expected to have values corresponding to instrument temperature; the Temp Channel-bw sensor, defined as STC Optical Bench (OB) in EGSE [RD.7] is located on the back side of one folding mirrors as in Figure 3-b and gives a measure of the OB temperature in the front part of the STC channel "Ch-Low".

Figure 3: In (a) the location of the "STC Temperature Channel-fw/FPA Package" (NSS21043) temperature sensor (red rectangle). As highlighted in the 3D CAD model (no pictures are available, it is not present in the original CAD model), this sensor is placed onto the FPA package, in the same position where the corresponding sensor is placed on the HRIC FPA. In (b) the location of the "STC Temperature Channel-bw/ STC Optical Bench" (NSS21044) temperature sensor, as shown in the 3D CAD model (no picture available).

- **VIHI**

PACKET ID: YSS40003		
Param ID	Param Name	Unit
NSS31040	Temperature FPA1	K
NSS31041	Temperature FPA2	K
NSS31042	Temperature PE	K
NSS31062	Temp Spectrometer	K
NSS31063	Temp Calibration unit	K

Table 5: Main VIHI temperature sensors.

See [RD.8] for more details on their definition and position.

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3.SIMBIO-SYS Interchannel Test

3.1. SIMBIO-SYS Interference Test

3.1.1. Test description

The goal of this test it to study:

- the dependence of HRIC/STC detector reset level fluctuation with respect to their different configurations of Integration and Repetition Time
- the presence and the influence of such noise also while VIHI is operating (not tested previously).

The following configurations have been defined:

- Phase 1:

STC and HRIC channels acquire images respectively for the Win-X and a window of size 256x256 (CBD=128x128).

HRIC tested two configurations:

- Integration Time (IT) = 480 us, Repetition Time (RT) = 1s for at least 5 minutes
- IT = 480, RT = 1.5s for at least 7 minutes

STC one configuration

- IT = 105.6 us, RT = 1s in continuous mode acquisitions in parallel to both HRIC configurations. Acquisitions are stopped with a STOP TC after 12 minutes from the beginning of the STC acquisitions (i.e., 5 minutes + 7 minutes = 12 minutes)

- Phase 2:

In the second phase VIHI is switched on and after 18 minutes it starts acquiring. The test repeated the previous phase with the synchronic acquisition of VIHI channel (with window size 64x256) with IT = 146 (RAW), RT = 0.5s for at least 12 minutes

All acquisitions were performed with IBR=8.

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Phases and configurations are depicted in Figure 4.

Figure 4 Scheme of the configuration tested by Interchannel test. Phase 1 and Phase 2 are separated by the Switch On (dotted red arrow) of VIHI Channel.

3.1.2. Commanding

Despite the Interchannel test was the last test to be executed in ICO#04b (see [RD.1] for details), all channels were in OFF state. So, before executing the test, it was necessary to switch-on all the channels.

After that, the test has been performed through the execution of a PDORs named: "POR_BPSS00793_SIMBIOSYS_ALL_ICO#04bis_interference_test" (see attachments of [RD.1]).

A detailed timeline of the test is shown in Table 6.

Timing	Duration [min]	FOP ID	FOP Name	RT [raw]	HRIC sector	STC sector	VIHI sector
08:55:00	12	ASSF320A	STC-Filter-X	200	-	1	-
08:55:01	5	ASSF100A	HRIC Science	200	1	1	-
09:00:02	7	ASSF100A	HRIC Science	300	2	1	-
09:25:00	12	ASSF512A	VIHI Science	100	-	-	1

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09:25:01	12:02	ASSF320A	STC-Filter-X	200	-	2	1
09:25:02	5	ASSF100A	HRIC Science	200	3	2	1
09:30:03	7	ASSF100A	HRIC Science	300	4	2	1

Table 6: Timeline of the ICO#04b interchannel test with the references to the commanded FOPs (see [RD.9] for more details).

The resulting executions TeleCommand (TC) database derived by means of the Electric Ground Segment Equipment (EGSE) telemetry-to-raw pipeline is reported in Table 7, Table 8 and Table 9 (see [RD.7] for details).

EGSE_TC#	1 st acq (UTC)	Duration	# acq
1	2021-04-24 08:55:01.042013	5 minutes	300
2	2021-04-24 09:00:02.042716	7 minutes	280
3	2021-04-24 09:25:02.043345	5 minutes	300
4	2021-04-24 09:30:03.039867	7 minutes	281

Table 7: Resulting database of the Interchannel Test for the HRIC channel.

EGSE_TC#	1 st acq (UTC)	Duration	# acq
1	2021-04-24 08:55:00.042059	12 minutes	720
2	2021-04-24 09:25:01.043208	12 minutes and 2 seconds	722

Table 8: Resulting database of the Interchannel Test for the STC channel.

EGSE_TC#	1 st acq (UTC)	Duration (s)	# acq
1	2021-04-24 09:25:00.043360	12 minutes	1440

Table 9: Resulting database of the Interchannel Test for the VIHI channel.

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The only anomaly was the occurrence of a well know error on the SpaceWire (SpW) between the SIMBIO-SYS ME and the VIHI PE at the end of the test while powering off VIHI. Nevertheless, the anomaly was correctly managed by the ME ASW.

3.1.3. HK Interpretation

Figure 5 and Figure 6 report the sensors temperature and TEC current evolution for the HRIC channel during the test while using the new uploaded parameters for the TEC “soft” activation.

All HK are reported science TEC switch on 2021-04-24T08:37:04 with HK sampling of 30s.

Figure 5: HRIC Temperatures evolution over the ICO#04b interchannel test.

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Figure 6: HRIC Tec current evolution over the ICO#04b interchannel test.

Figure 5 and Figure 6 show a **nominal trend for the FPA temperature and TEC current of HRIC channel** no Out-Of-Limit (OOL) in the current profile occurred (i.e., no peak).

Figure 7 and Figure 8 report the sensors temperature and TEC current evolution for the STC channel during the test.

All HK are reported science TEC switch on 2021-04-24T08:37:04 with HK sampling of 30s.

Figure 7: STC Temperatures evolution over the Orbit Test.

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Figure 8: STC TEC current evolution over the Orbit Test.

In Figure 7 and Figure 8 show, **as per the HRIC channel, a nominal trend for the FPA temperature and TEC current.**

Figure 9, Figure 10 and Figure 11 report the sensors temperature and TEC current evolution for the VIHI channel during the test.

All HK are reported science first VIHI HK 2021-04-24T09:09:12 with HK sampling of 10s.

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Figure 9: VIHI Temperature evolution over Inter-channel test.

Figure 10: VIHI TEC current evolution over inter-channel test

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Figure 11: VIHI Voltage.

As per STC and HRIC channel, their behaviour is nominal.

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3.1.4. Data Analysis

Figure 12 shows the mean DC values for all the SIMBIO-SYS channels during the Interference Test. In the first part (left side) the output of HRIC/STC parallel operations while in the second part (right side) the results for all channel acquisitions.

Figure 12: Mean DC values for all the channels during all the Interference Test.

Next image shows both in the case of Phase 1 and Phase 2 (see Figure 4 for details) the mean value of the Dark Current (DC) for each acquisition of the two cameras. Both plots cover a time of 12.5 minutes.

STC (always commanded with a RT=1s) is depicted in green. While the slower frame acquisitions of HRIC (RT=1s) are depicted in orange and the faster in red.

Note that in the two phases the timeline is the same a part the fact that in the same time of Phase 2 VIHI in acquiring in continuous mode.

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Figure 13: DC trends for the two cameras during the first (a) and last (b) phases of the test.

Note that during **Phase 1** the second TC of HRIC change the RT from 1s to 1.5s. After that the two cameras are acquired synchronically 1 time every two acquisition of STC. In all these occasions this generates **an interference on the DC of STC**.

During the **Phase 2** the same configurations are tested with VIHI in science continuous mode. As shown in Figure 13 (b) this generates **a noisy interference to both the channel**.

Limiting the analysis to Phase 1 this noise can be interpreted as a time shift of all the data acquire synchronically with HRIC channel as shown in Figure 14.

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(a)

(b)

Figure 14: Mean DC of the win-X of STC. In (a) DC is separated in the acquisitions in interference with HRIC and the ones acquired without the interference. In (b) the same plot shifting of 24 seconds backward the interfered ones (the orange).

Finally, as part of the test, **considering only the VIHI data** (see below plot extraction from Figure 12) **it is confirmed that no fluctuation of the detect reset level is present** (see [RD.8] for details).

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Figure 15: VIHI mean DC value during all the Interference Test.

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4. Conclusions

During the SIMBIO-SYS ICO#04b it was requested by the SIMBIO-SYS team to repeat the Interchannel test performed during previous ICO04 [RD.2] that failed due to an issue occurred to the VIHI channel (see [RD.3] for details).

This time, **the tests was executed without any issue apart from a communication error between ME and VIHI PE at the end.**

Obtained data:

- 1. Confirm the presence of a mutual interference between HRIC and STC while operating in parallel.**
- 2. Once also the VIHI channel operates in parallel the interference effect is higher on both cameras**
3. The VIHI channel seems to not be affected by the Low frequency Behaviour (LFB) (see [RD.11])

For the time being, some inferences have been done to explain/model the interference effect on the camera (i.e., data time-shift?) but additional analyses and test may be required.